

DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL AND HEALTH TOURISM IN THE RAPID DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM POTENTIAL OF THE REPUBLIC

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Annotation. This article is based on the fact that the creation of modern conditions in the formation of a tourist market based on the sustainable development of health tourism and wellness services is associated with various opportunities and problems of modern management of resort cities. Feedback from experts from all over the world on the development of field activities is devoted to such issues as the growth of medical and wellness tourism today.

Keywords. Wellness tourism, tourist demand, tourist flows, sanatorium-resort services, health tourism, wellness.

Аннотация. Данная статья основана на том факте, что создание современных условий при формировании туристического рынка, основанного на устойчивом развитии оздоровительного туризма и велнес-услуг, связано с различными возможностями и проблемами современного управления курортными городами. Отзывы экспертов со всего мира о развитии выездной деятельности посвящены таким вопросам, как рост медицинского и оздоровительного туризма сегодня.

Ключевые слова. Оздоровительный туризм, туристский спрос, туристские потоки, санаторно-курортные услуги, оздоровительный туризм, велнес.

In the conditions of the rapid development of World Tourism, there is not only a significant increase in tourist flows, but also a significant expansion in the number of tourist routes, types of Tourism and tourist profiles, which reflects the constant segmentation of the tourist market. These processes indicate an increasing diversification of tourist demand and an appropriate diversification of tourist supply. Some routes are becoming more diversified, others are targeting their products to new target markets, while others are restoring lost brands. These processes completely cover resort routes around the world.

In the modern global tourist space, resort destinations are characterized by the variety and originality of their historical development, types and forms of medical and wellness tourism, types and technologies of services, target markets, the scope of targeted audience coverage, development trends.

Health and wellness tourism, as part of the tourist market, occupies a relatively small share in the global tourist flow, but it is impossible to provide accurate statistics. This is due to the presence of a large number of subtypes and forms of health tourism in different countries and regions of the world, for most of which, due to Nationally Determined characteristics, statistics are not maintained, as well as Special Studies on national specific types of medical and health services are not carried out. Thus, in our Republic, statistics on sanatorium-resort services are carried out only within the country, and even the concept of "resort" is interpreted differently in different cultures and areas of Tourism, and "sanatorium"

has no analogues in other cultures and areas, both as an infrastructure object and as a concept. All this, on the one hand, complicates the research and solution of the problems of managing resort routes, and on the other hand, shows the relevance of scientific projects and work in the field of resort activities and health tourism.

Today, the research carried out in many countries of the world is devoted to the sustainable development of resort directions and health tourism, which is due to the variety of opportunities that have created modern conditions for the development of the tourist market and the problems of modern management of resort cities. However, experts from all over the world note that today the growth of medical and wellness tourism is so rapid that the emerging publications on the problems of its development do not correspond to its diverse growth rates.

Throughout the history of Tourism, people have traveled for recreational purposes. The exact time of the origin of health tourism is unknown due to lack of written evidence. However, researchers agree that "wellness tourism is as ancient as ancient history and as modern as the future". Health tourism is both a traditional, historically shaped practice that defines the purpose of travel and a modern industry of a global scale. As a result of Medical Progress and the development of social means of communication, there are a wide range of opportunities and services provided by new technologies.

Modern medical and wellness tourism is aimed at health or improvement, and focuses on areas and facilities specializing in the provision of medical and wellness services: marine climatic resorts, balneological or balneoclimatic resorts, thermal resorts on lakes with warm water, sanatoriums and hospitals with mineral waters and mud, thermal springs, mountaineering and ski resorts.

UNWTO experts identify three main forms of health tourism:

- 1) Medical tourism (specialized clinical or specialized tourism);
- 2) Wellness (fitness and sports or spa and sports; mud or hydrotherapy, weight loss clinic, cosmetology clinic, physical education and fitness training as a spa specialty);
- 3) Rehabilitation and rehabilitation (specially grown feed or loam or loam as a convenient addition to your home or tourist site).

Health and wellness tourism is increasingly diversified, reflecting the segmentation of the tour.

In the last decade, medical tourism has become a new fast-growing segment of this type of Tourism and a large business that reaches millions of travelers every year. For many countries, medical tourism is a rapidly growing global industry, with a large income and attracting professionals of different medical profiles. All this reflects the growing demand for a wide range of medical services.

A specific trend in medical and wellness tourism is to diversify the demand of travelers and diversify it, reflecting the relevant segment of the market for the supply of medical and wellness services. A segmented approach to this type of Tourism reveals the consolidation and development of segments such as "therapeutic", "clinical", "medical", "wellness", "thermal", "wellness tourism", etc. Within the national tourism sectors, national specific terms can also be used to describe National segments of health tourism, such as "sanatorium" services in our country.

Modern tourists with health and wellness goals visit the same destinations and for the same reasons as they have been for centuries. For example, resort centers of the

Mediterranean, which visited to relax and restore physical and mental strength, ancient Indian Ayurveda, traditional healing in India, pilgrimage to Lourdes in France in search of miraculous healing.

At the same time, modern technologies and trends in the development of tourism, including diversification of demand and tourist consumption models, have brought new directions, options and problems to the health tourism industry. Tourists visiting Mediterranean resorts are now sent to Turkish hospitals equipped with the latest medical technologies for treatment. Tourists are heading to India today for high-tech cardio. According to the WHO, France is leading the world with the development of wellness tourism, the growing tourist demand for the services of French clinics in the world.

A significant trend in the development of health tourism is the addition of a growing number of countries and territories to the list of health tourism destinations.

Factors for the development and growth of health tourism include:

1) age demographics: in many rich countries of the world, the aging of the population increases the demand for wellness services. Elderly tourists will find ways to treat chronic diseases on the tourist routes of medical and wellness tourism without waiting lists and low prices for similar services;

2) increasing attention to "youth culture": in Western countries (especially in the USA), a "youth" culture has been formed, that is, the concept and ideology that it is necessary to look and be young and healthy at any age, to spread physical health, beauty, strength is promoted. This is manifested in the desire of people to delay the aging and appearance of the body, and people from their empty income turn into an important substance of expenses that they plan along with the costs of rest, buying real estate or luxury goods. Modern tourists expect positive changes from medical and wellness tourism and order cosmetic procedures and other anti-aging treatments;

3) the cost of medical and wellness services (an important factor in medical tourism): cost savings for those who do not have health insurance in their country, limited insurance or large discounts for medical care. For less money, such tourists can serve more carefully than at home, including well-equipped residential buildings for themselves and their companions;

4) more convenience of tourism: the decline in air tariffs around the world, including the entry of discount airlines into the market, made tourism open to mass travelers, including "medical" tourists. Today there is a situation where people are more aware of the opportunities in the field of Health and wellness services and more people have the desire and opportunity to travel.

An important trend in the development of health tourism is the more effective impact of tourism on the target economy, the rise in the level of medical care and health care in general, which means the improvement of the quality of life of local residents of communities that accept tourists. Tourists receive high-quality medical care at an acceptable price, and the funds they spend fuel other tourism sectors, medical services, as well as the local economy, and can improve the health of the population in countries with a tourist route.

Modern medical and wellness tourism has a number of problems, notably: physician responsibility, service reliability, medical privacy, financial responsibility, safety (in some countries, medical services are experimental or even dangerous and prohibited). A serious problem is that in a world where health is increasingly seen as a commodity, tourists are buying illegal medical products (such as transplant authorities).

An excellent trend in the development of medical and wellness tourism is the rapid growth of such a segment as resort tourism. Experts say that it not only serves to prevent diseases or treat chronic diseases, but also increases harmony and human endurance.

The expectations of tourists in resort tourism can be classified as follows:

- 1) time spent in a calm and peaceful environment;
- 2) rest and relaxation in comfort and quality;
- 3) benefits from "waters" for personal health and well-being;
- 4) sense of security and care;
- 5) professional and qualified personnel;
- 6) quality compliance of the price.

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